

Research

Research on mechanical properties and pinning parameter optimization of Z-pinning PLA specimen based on FFF 3D-printing

Sunny Md Abu Saleh^{1*}, Zhiyong Ma²

¹School of Engineering, Huzhou University, Huzhou, Zhejiang 313000, China

Abstract: 3D printing technology made it possible to create intricately shaped, highly customized items, and it fundamentally altered the industrial sector. The mechanical anisotropy of 3D-printed parts, particularly the reduced strength in the construction direction (Z) direction, remains a persistent challenge. Layer-by-layer printing significantly reduces the strength along the Z-axis compared to the X and Y axes. Bending strength and compressive strength decline by around 25-35% and 20-30%, respectively, along the Z-axis, while tensile strength might fall as low as 25-50% of that in the horizontal orientations. Because of these restrictions, 3D-printed parts are less suitable for load-bearing applications, which highlights the urgent need for increased Z-axis strength. In order to address the problem of poor inter-layer bonding in 3D-printed PLA (poly-lactic acid) composites, a unique method called Z-pinning is applied in this study. Z-pinning technology involves creating circular voids in the layers and filling them with material to form pins, reinforcing inter-layer bonding. A range of models with varying pin diameters, lengths, and spacing were designed and tested to evaluate the impact of Z-pinning on mechanical performance. Using a consistent 0.4 mm nozzle and 0.15 mm layer height, we printed pinned parts alongside solid (unpinned) models. These were then subjected to tensile, bending, and compressive strength tests. Comparison of the Z-pinned and unpinned specimens revealed a tensile strength increase of approximately 46.39% in pinned models and an 18.3% improvement in bending strength. Although compressive strength showed a more modest increase of 8.02%, the overall gains in tensile and bending strength underscore the effectiveness of the Z-pinning technique.

Keywords: 3D-printing, Z-pinning technology, mechanical properties, parameter optimization.

*Corresponding Author

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1. Introduction

Since extrusion-based additive manufacturing techniques, such as Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF), can quickly create complex, customized parts, they have become integral to modern production [1,2]. FFF's widespread availability makes it ideal for both functional components and prototypes, with polylactic acid (PLA) being one of its most popular materials due to its biodegradability and ease of use [3,4]. However, FFF introduces a key challenge:

mechanical anisotropy, particularly reduced strength along the Z-axis (Table 1), which limits FFF-printed PLA's suitability for load-bearing applications [5,6]. This anisotropy results from FFF's layer-by-layer deposition, where each new layer bonds primarily through thermal fusion, creating weaker interfaces along the Z-axis [7,8]. As seen in Table 1, while material cohesion and tensile strength in the X-Y plane are relatively strong, the Z-axis often shows 40-60% lower strength, making it prone to delamination [9]. Process parameters such as extrusion temperature, print speed, and layer height, layer thickness also influence this inter-layer adhesion, with higher speeds and thicker layers further weakening Z-axis strength [10,11,12]. In response, researchers have explored multiple methods to enhance Z-axis strength in FFF parts, among which Z-pinning (Fig. 1) has shown substantial promise. As seen in Fig. 1, Z-pinning introduces vertical pins of material at regular intervals, creating continuous reinforcements across multiple layers that act like mechanical fasteners, enhancing inter-layer adhesion [13]. Studies by Yu Gao et al. (2022) demonstrated that continuous fiber pins could significantly improve tensile strength in thermoplastics, with angled pins at 45° resulting in up to a 10% increase in tensile strength and a 7.16% improvement in fracture toughness [14]. This study focuses on evaluating and optimizing the mechanical properties of Z-pinned PLA parts created through FFF, specifically targeting Z-axis strength improvements via optimized pin configurations. By adjusting pin length, diameter, and spacing, this research aims to make FFF-printed PLA components more structurally robust and suitable for demanding applications. This approach involves inserting pins made from the same material as the printed part, such as PLA, into pre-designed voids or channels that span multiple layers (Fig. 1) [15]. As shown in Fig. 1, the process begins with a 3D model in which pinning locations are predefined along the Z-axis. The printer constructs the part layer by layer, creating specific voids at designated intervals to align vertically (Fig. 1a) and act as pin placements, ensuring uniform reinforcement throughout [16]. Once a set of layers reaches the required pin length, the printer pauses, repositions the nozzle, and fills the voids via continuous extrusion (Fig. 1b), forming solid columns through several layers [17]. Following this insertion, As shown in Fig. 1c, the printer resumes regular layer-by-layer printing without further voids, referred to as "pin spacing" which defines the distance between consecutive pins in the Z direction (Fig. 1c). This spacing balances reinforcement and material efficiency, ensuring pins are distributed effectively. After completing these layers, the printer resumes creating new voids for subsequent pin placements. As shown in Fig. 1d, this repetitive cycle of void creation, filling, and regular printing extends throughout the part, generating a consistent Z-axis reinforcement pattern. By acting as connectors between layers, the Z-pins counteract the common Z-axis weakness in FFF-printed parts, where insufficient inter-layer adhesion often limits structural strength. This study systematically examines Z-pinning to determine optimal pin parameters such as pin length, diameter, and spacing aimed at producing a robust Z-axis in FFF-printed PLA components, ultimately advancing additive manufacturing techniques that address the inherent limitations of FFF in load-bearing applications.

Table 1: Mechanical anisotropy of extrusion-based printed samples.

Material	Printing Platform	Tensile Strength (X-Axis)	Tensile Strength (Z-Axis)	Reduction (%)	Reference
PLA	FFF	56.0 MPA	24.0 MPA	57%	[18]
PLA	FFF	55.0 MPA	37.0 MPA	33%	[19]
15% CF-PLA	FFF	53.0 MPA	35.0 MPA	34%	[19]

Fig. 1: Process for z-pinning using FFF extrusion.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1 Materials and Equipment

In this study, Creality CR-PLA white filament with a diameter of 1.75 mm was used for printing all specimens (Table 2). As seen in Table 2, the key properties of the PLA material include a density of $1.25 \pm 0.05 \text{ g/cm}^3$, a melt flow rate of 5–7 g/min (at 190°C and 2.16 kg), and water absorption at 0.5%, as summarized in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the printing was conducted on an Ender 3 S1 Pro printer equipped with a 0.4 mm nozzle, which ensured consistent extrusion and layer bonding. SolidWorks software was employed to design both 2D and 3D models. The slicing and G-code preparation were completed using Creality Slicer version 4.8.2, with additional G-code modifications done in Repetier-Host software.

Table 2: Properties of PLA filament and equipment specifications.

Property	Value
Material density	$1.25 \pm 0.05 \text{ g/cm}^3$
Melt Flow Rate	5–7 g/min (190°C, 2.16 kg)
Water Absorption	0.50%
Filament Diameter	1.75 mm
Printer Model	Ender 3 S1 Pro
Nozzle Diameter	0.4 mm
Software	SolidWorks, Repetier-Host, Creality Slicer 4.8.2

2.2 Experimental Model and Specimen Setup

2.2.1 Pinned and unpinned model

Both pinned and unpinned models were designed in SolidWorks following national standards for tensile (GB/T 1040-92 II), compressive (GB/T 1041-2008), and bending tests (GB/T 9341-2008). The unpinned models contained no internal voids or reinforcement pins and served as a control group to establish a baseline for comparing mechanical performance with the pinned models (Fig. 2a). The outer dimensions of both pinned and unpinned models were consistently similar across all test types to ensure that any performance differences could be attributed solely to the Z-pinning technique (Fig. 2a). As shown in Fig. 2b, the pinned models were specifically designed to incorporate Z-pins as reinforcements, with pins arranged in precise configurations to assess their influence on the mechanical performance of the parts. To keep the comparison with the control group valid, the outer dimensions of the pinned models remained consistent with the unpinned models across all test types, as seen in Fig. 2. How many columns and rows of pins were added was decided by the width and thickness of the model. For the bending models, because of the 15 mm width and 4 mm thickness, four columns of pins were added. For the tensile models, due to the 12 mm middle width, three columns of pins were used. The compressive models, with an 8 mm thickness, had two rows, each containing four columns of pins. These configurations were designed to optimize Z-axis reinforcement for each loading condition.

Fig. 2: Design overview for (a) outer dimensions for pinned and unpinned model (b) Z-pin Placement for pinned model.

2.2.2 Pinning Variations and Configurations

In this study, three primary pinning parameters pin length, diameter, and spacing were systematically varied to assess their influence on the mechanical properties of 3D-printed PLA parts. These variations resulted in multiple combinations, each created for the bending, tensile, and compressive tests. As shown in Fig. 3, the number of pins within each specimen depended on the available length or thickness (for compressive parts) as well as the specific pinning configuration, which alternated between rows and columns to create uniform reinforcement. As shown in Table 1, the variations resulted in a total of 36 pinned configurations for each test type. This full factorial design (4 pin lengths \times 3 diameters \times 3 distances) ensured a comprehensive analysis of the effects of each pinning parameter on mechanical performance (Table 3).

Pin configurations were arranged in a systematic, staggered pattern to optimize inter-layer bonding while maintaining even reinforcement throughout each part (Fig. 3). The staggered pinning technique shown in Fig. 3, represented by an alternating sequence of pins and spacings, labeled as "A" (pin length) and "B" (distance between pins), was designed to distribute mechanical stress evenly and prevent direct overlap of pins in adjacent columns. This approach differed slightly based on the number of columns needed in each part, as shown in Fig. 3.

Table 3: Parameters for the Z-pins that will be used in the pinned models.

Parameter	Variations
Pin Length (L)	6 mm, 6.5 mm, 7 mm, 7.5 mm
Pin Diameter (D)	2 mm, 2.5 mm, 3 mm
Distance Between Pins (Pd)	1 mm, 1.5 mm, 2 mm

Fig. 3: Staggering of z-pins in the A/B configuration for (a) bending, (b) tensile, and (c) compressive parts.

2.3 Printing procedure

2.3.1 Printer setup

The FFF printing process was used to construct each part by depositing PLA filament layer by layer. As shown in Table 4, a layer height of 0.15 mm was selected, balancing print quality, mechanical strength, and time efficiency. The extrusion temperature was maintained between 210°C and 215°C to facilitate smooth material flow and effective layer adhesion (Table 4). The bed temperature was set to 65°C to prevent warping and ensure strong adhesion of the first layer. An infill density of 70% was used (Table 4) to provide adequate internal support while optimizing print time. As shown in Table 4, a print speed of 80 mm/s was selected for standard layer deposition, which provided a balance between print time and surface quality. However, during the extrusion of material into the Z-pins, the print speed was reduced to 40 mm/s (Table 4) to ensure precise material placement and effective integration of the Z-pins into the printed layers.

Table 4: Parameters and setting for printing procedure.

Parameter	Value	Reason
Layer Height	0.15 mm	Balanced print resolution, strength, and time
Nozzle Diameter	0.4 mm	Ensured precision in extrusion
Extrusion Temperature	210–215°C	Optimized for smooth flow and adhesion
Bed Temperature	65°C	Ensured proper first-layer adhesion
Print Speed (Normal)	80 mm/s	Balanced quality and speed for regular layers
Print Speed (Z-pins)	40 mm/s	Precise extrusion into the Z-pins
Infill Density	70%	Provided adequate support without excess material

2.3.2 Incorporation of Z-Pins

The CAD models shown in Fig. 4 were modified in SolidWorks to integrate voids into the printed parts, ensuring they would accommodate the Z-pins. As shown in Fig. 4, these voids were positioned according to the experimental design matrix, which specified parameters such as pin length, diameter, and spacing. To achieve precise placement, the initial CAD models included both the voids and the Z-pins as separate bodies within the voids (Fig. 4a). Designing the pins separately allowed the pin axis to be easily distinguished during the 3D design process (Fig. 4b), providing accurate control over Z-pin placement. To incorporate the Z-pins, the first step involved extracting the G-code from a model that contained both voids and separate pin bodies. Since the pins were modeled as separate entities, this initial G-code identified the starting coordinates of the pin axis, which provided the precise X, Y, and Z locations for each pin. A second G-code file was then generated from a model containing only the voids. This G-code was subsequently modified to enable continuous extrusion within the voids, effectively creating the Z-pins. For implementing Z-pinning in the actual printing process, the G-code was modified using Repetier Host software. Precision was essential during the extrusion of the Z-pins, so the extrusion speed was reduced to 2400 mm/min, compared to the standard printing speed of 4800 mm/min. The lower speed allowed for better control over material flow, minimizing the risk of over-extrusion or under-extrusion and ensuring that each void was accurately filled. Once the nozzle moved to the specified X, Y, and Z coordinates for each void, the G-code instructed the printer to extrude the exact volume of material needed to form the Z-pin. To determine the required length of filament (L) for filling each void volume (V), the applied formula:

$$L = \frac{V}{A} \quad (1)$$

where A represents the filament's cross-sectional area.

This calculation allowed for precise material use, ensuring that each Z-pin fully occupied the designated void space.

Fig. 4: Schematic of SolidWorks design with (a) model for pin location, (b) Z-pins, and (c) model for z-pin extrusion.

2.4 Mechanical Test

The Instron 5966 machine (Fig. 5a) with a three-point bending fixture was used, adhering to the requirements of the GB/T 9341-2008 standard for the bending test. The specimen was supported at both ends with a span of 50 mm (Fig. 5a), and a load was applied at the center with a loading speed of 2 mm/min. Proper alignment of the specimen was crucial to prevent premature failure, which could occur if the specimen slipped or if the load was not evenly distributed. For the tensile test, the CMT 6103 machine was used, in accordance with the GB/T 1040-92 II standard (Fig. 5b). As shown in Fig. 5b, the specimens were clamped securely at both ends to prevent slippage, which could otherwise affect the results. The dog-bone shape of the tensile specimens ensured that failure occurred in the narrow middle section, where the material was subjected to the highest stress. The gauge length was set to 34 mm, and the cross-head speed for the test was 5 mm/min (Fig. 5b). Compressive strength tests were conducted using the MTS 810 Material Test System (Fig. 5c), with specimens oriented vertically and compressed along the Z-axis according to GB/T 1041-2008. The setup involved placing the specimens between two flat plates, with the top plate applying a compressive force until the specimen failed. Special attention was given to aligning the specimens to ensure an even distribution of force, avoiding skewed results due to uneven loading. The loading speed was set to 20 mm/min (Fig. 5c), and the tests continued until the strain reached 70%.

Fig. 5: Mechanical testing: (a) Instron 5966 machine and bending specimen, (b) CMT 6103 machine and tensile specimen, and (c) MTS 810 machine and compressive specimen.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Mechanical Properties and Comparative Analysis

The mechanical performance of Z-pinned and solid (unpinned) specimens in Table 5 shows clear distinctions in bending, tensile, and compressive strengths. In Table 5, the 36 Z-pinned configurations were placed based on variations in pin length, spacing, and diameter to systematically investigate how each parameter influences the structural integrity of 3D-printed parts. By carefully analyzing each configuration, it was possible to observe how specific pinning characteristics affect mechanical behavior, particularly along the Z-axis. Table 5 provides a comprehensive overview, showing how each Z-pinning configuration's mechanical properties compare to the solid specimen.

To evaluate the mechanical performance of both pinned and unpinned specimens, they are presented side by side in Fig. 6. In Fig. 6, the right side of the box shows the series name, where each configuration is represented by a combination of pin length, spacing, and diameter (e.g., $(7*1*3)$, where 7 is the pin length, 1 is the pin spacing, and 3 is the pin diameter). In Fig. 6, the first series represents the mechanical strength of the solid (unpinned) specimen, the next three series show the specimens with the lowest mechanical strength, followed by those with medium mechanical strength, and finally, the last three series with the highest mechanical strength. With a total of 36 Z-pinned specimens, this grouping approach simplifies data presentation. In Fig. 6. a, it is observed that the specimen with a $(6*2*2)$ pinning configuration had the lowest bending strength, showing a -27.05% decrease compared to the solid part, while the highest bending strength was found in the $(7*2*3)$ configuration, which exhibited an 18.31% increase over the solid specimen. As shown in Fig. 6. b, the specimen with the $(6.5*1*2.5)$ pinning configuration showed the lowest tensile force, with a -4.873% decrease compared to the solid specimen, the specimen with the highest tensile force had a $(6*1.5*3)$ pinning configuration, exhibiting a $+48.538\%$ increase compared to the solid part (Fig. 6b).

Table 5: Mechanical test results of the pinned and unpinned specimens.

Sp: No	Pin Length (mm)	Pin Spacing (mm)	Pin Diameter (mm)	Bending Strength (MPA)	Tensile Strength (MPA)	Compressive Strength (MPA)
1	7.5	1.0	3.0	90.27±6.43	31.05±0.05	167.55±0.85
2	7.5	1.5	3.0	94.53±1.53	32.60 ±3.00	169.30±1.00
3	7.5	2.0	3.0	94.43±5.30	30.10±2.50	164.50±3.70
4	7.5	1.0	2.5	72.47±4.05	27.15±1.45	164.25±6.45
5	7.5	1.5	2.5	66.22±1.91	27.80 ±0.20	167.85±4.45
6	7.5	2.0	2.5	71.64±4.97	36.50 ±0.70	160.15±1.65
7	7.5	1.0	2.0	67.51±10.60	33.55±0.75	160.55±1.35
8	7.5	1.5	2.0	73.88±6.67	31.20 ±3.10	159.50±2.50
9	7.5	2.0	2.0	65.39±1.66	32.85±1.65	160.05±0.25
10	7.0	1.0	3.0	96.58±4.19	32.65±1.65	158.75±0.45
11	7.0	1.5	3.0	95.00 ±8.73	34.25±1.35	164.60 ±0.70
12	7.0	2.0	3.0	100.26±0.91	37.55±1.25	157.20±2.20
13	7.0	1.0	2.5	81.95±1.05	28.10 ±2.10	162.85±2.35
14	7.0	1.5	2.5	82.74±1.04	26.10 ±0.90	168.45±4.15
15	7.0	2.0	2.5	74.97±1.74	28.65±0.75	160.55±3.05
16	7.0	1.0	2.0	68.21±0.33	30.05±1.65	164.05±7.05
17	7.0	1.5	2.0	78.35±1.61	31.40±1.50	158.15±2.05
18	7.0	2.0	2.0	81.08±1.30	29.45±0.85	158.7±0.50
19	6.5	1.0	3.0	90.23±7.37	35.25±1.65	170.65±1.05
20	6.5	1.5	3.0	97.24±6.34	30.95±2.55	172.30 ±0.20
21	6.5	2.0	3.0	95.23±8.03	36.30±4.10	163.95±2.15
22	6.5	1.0	2.5	69.50±6.22	24.40 ±1.30	166.00 ±0.70
23	6.5	1.5	2.5	71.31±6.03	28.30 ±2.00	169.80±2.20
24	6.5	2.0	2.5	76.31±2.82	27.70 ±1.60	163.20 ±1.40
25	6.5	1.0	2.0	64.35±0.51	31.35±2.45	161.80±1.80
26	6.5	1.5	2.0	74.92±11.32	33.60 ±1.80	159.95±4.15
27	6.5	2.0	2.0	69.95±3.38	30.95±0.75	166.20±2.00
28	6.0	1.0	3.0	99.64±0.71	33.60±1.80	163.15±4.85
29	6.0	1.5	3.0	96.20±7.34	38.10 ±0.70	164.35±1.55
30	6.0	2.0	3.0	93.02±8.41	32.00 ±3.10	160.30±2.80
31	6.0	1.0	2.5	67.8±0.23	33.20±0.50	161.80±6.00
32	6.0	1.5	2.5	62.01±1.28	31.05±1.55	162.05±2.85
33	6.0	2.0	2.5	77.09±5.61	30.55±1.60	162.10±0.40
34	6.0	1.0	2.0	68.91±7.63	30.55±1.60	160.75±3.65
35	6.0	1.5	2.0	75.86±11.24	34.05±1.95	163.70±5.80
36	6.0	2.0	2.0	61.81±1.53	31.35±2.65	171.50±4.00
Unpinned	-	-	-	84.74±1.81	25.65±2.65	159.50±6.50

During the compressive test, both pinned and unpinned specimens began to lose their shape at around 10 kN of pressure. However, each pinned specimen took longer to deform. The (7*2*3) specimen, even with lower compressive properties, took 6.9 seconds to deform, a much longer time than the unpinned specimen. The solid unpinned specimen began deforming earlier, at 6.1 seconds, despite having a slightly higher compressive strength compared to the (7*2*3) pinned specimen. This result suggests that the Z-pinned specimens displayed a form of anti-deformation property. As shown in Fig. 6c, the compressive specimen with a (7*2*3) pinning configuration had the lowest compressive strength, showing a -1.442% decrease compared to the solid specimen, while the specimen with a (6.5*1.5*3) pinning configuration had the highest compressive strength, with an +8.025% increase over the solid specimen.

Fig. 6: (a) Bending, (b) tensile, and (c) compressive strength comparison charts between pinned and unpinned specimen.

3.2 Discussion of Optimal Structure

3.2.1 Optimization of Z-Pinning Parameters

(1) Effect of Pin Diameter on Mechanical Properties

The study revealed that specimens with a pin diameter of 3 mm demonstrated superior bending strength (Fig. 7) compared to those with smaller diameters of 2 mm and 2.5 mm. The larger cross-sectional area of the 3 mm pin enhances structural integrity, effectively distributing force across layers and reducing the likelihood of premature failure, particularly along the Z-axis, where inter-layer adhesion is typically weaker. The combination of a 3 mm pin diameter with shorter pin lengths, such as 6 mm and 7 mm, provided the best bending performance (Fig. 7a). Additionally, in Fig. 7b, specimens with 6.5 mm and 7 mm pin lengths, combined with a 3 mm pin diameter, exhibited notable improvements in tensile strength, likely due to the increased contact area between the pin and surrounding material, which promotes load distribution along the Z-axis. For compressive strength, the anti-deformation performance of the specimens was significantly enhanced with a 3 mm pin diameter. As seen in Fig. 7c, 3 mm pins particularly when combined with shorter pin lengths such as 6 mm and 6.5 mm provided superior compressive strength, effectively resisting deformation under compressive loads.

(a) (b)

(c)

Fig. 7: Effect of pin diameter in (a) bending, (b) tensile, and (c) compressive specimens.

(2) Effect of Pin Length on Mechanical Properties

Though longer pin lengths of 7 mm and 7.5 mm performed reasonably well (Fig. 8), the difference among the four pin length configurations was minimal. As seen in Fig. 8a, for bending strength, shorter pin lengths, particularly 7 mm combined with a 3 mm diameter and 1 mm or 1.5 mm pin spacing, demonstrated significant improvements. In tensile chart, Fig. 8b, it's seen that the 6 mm pin length consistently delivered strong performance, with the lowest tensile strength still showing a 19.103% increase over unpinned specimens. Configurations with pin lengths of 6.5, 7, and 7.5 mm, particularly when paired with a 2.5 mm diameter, showed the weakest tensile performance (Fig. 8b). In compressive strength chart (Fig. 8c), shorter pins such as 6 mm and 6.5 mm exhibited better anti-deformation properties, effectively resisting structural collapse under load. As seen in Fig. 8c, the 6.5 mm pin length emerged as optimal for compressive performance, functioning effectively as an anti-deformation mechanism.

(a) (b)

(c)

Fig. 8: Effect of the pin length in (a) bending, (b) tensile, and (c) compressive specimens.

(3) Effect of Distance Between Pins on Mechanical Properties.

For bending and tensile strength, pin spacing had a relatively minor effect on mechanical performance. However, configurations with pin spacings of 1 mm and 1.5 mm paired with a 3 mm pin diameter resulted in higher bending and tensile strengths (Fig. 9). Fig. 9 shows that smaller pin spacings, specifically 1 mm and 1.5 mm, provided the best resistance to compressive forces. As pin spacing increased to 2 mm, a noticeable decline in compressive strength was observed, suggesting that tighter pin arrangements enhance the specimen’s ability to resist deformation under load.

Fig. 9: Effect of the distance between pins in compressive specimens.

3.2.2 Optimal Parameters

As it seen from the Table 6, different pin configurations yield the best results for each mechanical test. The highest bending strength was achieved with a pin length of 7 mm, a 3 mm pin diameter, and 2 mm spacing, resulting in an 18.31% improvement (Table 6). For tensile strength, the optimal configuration was a 6 mm pin length, 3 mm diameter, and 1.5 mm spacing, which produced an impressive 48.54% increase (Table 6). Similarly, the best compressive strength was found with 6.5 mm pin length, 3 mm diameter, and 1.5 mm spacing, leading to an 8.03% improvement in compressive strength (Table 6).

Table 6: Optimal Z-Pinning parameters for bending, tensile, and compressive Strength.

Test	Pin Length (mm)	Pin Diameter (mm)	Pin Spacing (mm)	Strength Improvement (%)
Bending	7	3	2	18.31
Tensile	6	3	1.5	48.54
Compressive	6.5	3	1.5	8.03
Overall Best	6.5	3	1.5	25.63 (average)

3.3 Impact of Z-Pinning on Mechanical Properties

According to the test results presented in Table 7, a comparative analysis of the mechanical performance of solid (unpinned) specimens and Z-pinned specimens reveals significant improvements in tensile, bending, and compressive strengths. As shown in Table 7 and Fig. 10, incorporating Z-pins into 3D-printed parts led to notable increases across all tested properties. Among the Z-pinned specimens, the best tensile strength was found to be 48.54% higher than the unpinned specimen (Table 7). Similarly, the highest bending strength showed an 18.31% increase (Table 7) compared to the solid part. For compressive strength, the top-performing specimen exhibited an 8.03% improvement over the unpinned parts (Table 7). Analysis of the top 10 pinning configurations in Fig. 10, further illustrates that, on average, Z-pinning increased bending strength by 13.44%, tensile strength by 37.97%, and compressive strength by 6.03%. These findings underscore the positive impact of Z-pinning on the mechanical performance of 3D-printed parts, particularly in enhancing Z-axis strength and overall structural resilience.

Table 7: Effect of Z-pin on the mechanical properties.

Properties	Variation	
	Maximum	Minimum
Tensile Strength	48.54%	-5.12%
Bending Strength	18.31%	-37.086%
Compressive Strength	8.03%	-1.463%

Fig. 10: Effect of Z-pin on the mechanical properties.

4. Conclusion

Z-pinning in Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) has demonstrated significant potential for reinforcing the Z-axis strength of 3D-printed polylactic acid (PLA) structures, particularly addressing the challenge of mechanical anisotropy. In this study, PLA specimens were fabricated with systematically varied Z-pin configurations, analyzing the effects of pin length, diameter, and spacing on tensile, bending, and compressive strengths. The FFF process utilized in this research incorporated precision G-code modifications and optimized parameters, allowing consistent placement of Z-pins throughout each layer and maximizing inter-layer bonding. The experimental results indicate that Z-pinning yields considerable improvements in mechanical performance along the Z-axis. Among the tested configurations, specimens with a 3 mm pin diameter displayed superior structural reinforcement compared to those with smaller diameters, effectively distributing force and reducing the likelihood of delamination. Specifically, a configuration with a 7 mm pin length, 2 mm spacing, and 3 mm diameter achieved the highest bending strength, showing an 18.31% increase compared to unpinned specimens. For tensile strength, the configuration with a 6 mm pin length, 1.5 mm spacing, and 3 mm diameter provided a 48.54% improvement, while the optimal compressive strength, an 8.03% increase, was observed with a 6.5 mm pin length, 1.5 mm spacing, and 3 mm diameter. These findings underscore that carefully controlled pin parameters can significantly enhance mechanical performance, particularly in resisting deformation under compressive loads. Compressive testing revealed that Z-pinned specimens delayed deformation by approximately 0.8 seconds longer than unpinned specimens under identical loads, suggesting improved resistance and structural resilience. An analysis of pin spacing and length further indicated that shorter pin lengths, particularly 6 mm and 6.5 mm, combined with smaller spacing of 1–1.5 mm, contributed to optimal tensile and compressive strength enhancements by improving inter-layer cohesion and reducing deformation risks.

Author Contributions:

Sunny Md Abu Saleh: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Formal Analysis, Data Correction, Writing—Original Draft Preparation, Writing—Review and Editing.

Zhiyong Ma: Supervision, Methodological Guidance, Research Material and Equipment Provision, Validation, Critical Feedback.

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Sunny Md Abu Saleh is a Master's degree student at the School of Engineering, Huzhou University, China, majoring in Intelligent Equipment and Automation Engineering. His research interests focus on additive manufacturing and mechanical design.

